

Section 1.

1.1 Samples description

Core	Total Clay	Quartz	Plagioclase	Calcite	Smectite	Illite + Muscovite	Chlorite + Kaolinite	Dolomite	Sum
	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%
3H5*	57.1	16.4	15.1	8.9		41.3	15.8	1.1	98.6
65X1*	30.9	46.7	18.5	1.1		22.6	8.3	2.6	99.8
24R3*	50.3	30.6	14.8	2.4		28.3	22	1.8	99.9
52R4**	58.5	24.3	13	4	8.6	36.4	13.5		99.8
58R2*	72.8	16	11.1		36.6	26.5	9.7		99.9
61R1*	90.2	3.7	5.5		75	4.4	10.8		99.4
69R6*	2.4	1		96.6		2.4			100
*this study									
** LIMS Report (http://web.iodp.tamu.edu/)									

Table 1. Summary of the lithologies and mineral composition LIMS report available at ¹). Mineral abundances in weight percent for Total clay, Quartz, Plagioclase, Calcite, Smectite, Illite and Muscovite, Chlorite and Kaolinite, Dolomite, and Sum. Smectite-rich samples of 61R are composed primarily of montmorillonite, whose expandability increases with depth. This is likely an indication of changing detrital source conditions and/or increasing the amount of authigenic smectite that formed from alteration of dispersed volcanic ash².

Core	Top depth	Total clay**	Quartz**	Plagioclase**	Calcite**	Smectite [^]	Illite [^]	Chlorite + Kaolinite [^]	Quartz [^]
	m	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%	wt.%
3H4*	19.6	44.9	7.8	5.4	41.9	30.4	57.1	7.3	5.2
65X1	485.5	59.1	25.7	13.8	1.4	□	□	□	□
24R3	971.3	63.4	22.3	13.2	1.0	46.1	44.3	7.5	2.1
52R4	1242.9	60.9	22.0	13.0	4.0	15.5	62.3	15.5	6.8
58R2	1291.2	68.0	18.8	11.7	1.5	83.2	16.8	0	0
61R1	1318.5	76.66	3.33	18.16	1.85	98.5	1.5	0	0
69R6	1398.7	0.0	0.1	0.9	99.0	□	□	□	□
* 19.5 cm above 3H5									
[^] Rosenberger et al 2020									
** LIMS report									

Table 2. Mineral abundances from LIMS report available at LIMS¹ integrated of clays mineralogy from Rosenberger et al.² Core: IODP sample identifier; Top depth: the depth of the top of the sample (m); Total clay, Quartz, Plagioclase, Calcite, from bulk samples XRPD (wt.%). Smectite, Illite, Chlorite and Kaolinite, Quartz, mineral contents from clay sized samples XRPD (wt.%).

In the tested materials, smectite increases significantly at depth > 1250 m whereas illite and quartz decrease. The smectite-rich samples are composed primarily of montmorillonite, expandability increases with depth

which is likely an indication of changing detrital source conditions and/or increasing the amount of authigenic smectite that formed from alteration of dispersed volcanic ash².

1.2 X-ray powder diffraction results of the starting materials

Figure 1. 3H5: quartz, calcite, mica (muscovite-illite), plagioclase, chlorite, kaolinite, dolomite, halite, smectite

Figure 2. 24R3: quartz, mica (muscovite-illite), plagioclase, chlorite, dolomite, calcite, kaolinite, k-feldspar, smectite

Figure 3. 58R2: quartz, mica (muscovite-illite), plagioclase, k-feldspar, kaolinite, smectite

Figure 4. 61R1-yellow: quartz, mica (muscovite-illite), nacrite-kaolinite, plagioclase, barite, smectite

Figure 5. 65X1: quartz, mica (muscovite-illite), plagioclase, k-feldspar, calcite, dolomite, chlorite, amphibole, kaolinite, halite, serpentinite

Figure 6. 69R6: calcite, quartz, phyllosilicates (low crystallinity)

1.3 Smear slides of starting materials

Samples from the cores were dried, disaggregated by hand, disaggregated with a pestle and mortar, and sieved to keep the fraction $<250\ \mu\text{m}$. Then, this fraction was mixed with distilled water. Drops of the mixture were placed on a sample holder, dried, and observed under a binocular microscope (Leica DMRXP and Euromex,). Quartz or feldspar grains of the size up to 0.17 mm were detected from the two samples of core 61R (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Smear slides of all tested lithologies before the experiment. Top panels: dried. Bottom panels: wet.

Figure 8. Enlargement of sample 61R showing vitreous grains, 0.10 mm in size, and clasts of 0.2 mm.

Smectite-rich samples in 61R are composed primarily of montmorillonite and likely form from alteration of volcanic ashes. The bulk of smectite is authigenic smectite², pseudomorph on glass grains, so that the global fabric is clastic with grains of ca. 0.2 mm diameter.

Reference list

1. JOIDES resolution science operator. LIMS report. *International Ocean Discovery Program* <https://web.iodp.tamu.edu/>.
2. Rosenberger, K., Underwood, M. B., Vrolijk, P. & Haines, S. Data report: clay mineral assemblages in hemipelagic sediments entering the Sumatra subduction zone, IODP Sites U1480 and U1481, Expedition 362. **362**, (2020).